

THE ROLE OF JAPANESE LANGUAGE SCHOOL (*NIHONGO GAKKOU*) IN JAPAN TO IMPROVING JLPT

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Abstract

Japanese is one of the foreign languages many Indonesians study, and at least 128 million people worldwide use Japanese. The number of Indonesian students studying Japanese reached 870 thousand students. This figure makes Indonesia the second largest country to learn Japanese after China. With a close diplomatic relationship for 61 years, Indonesian students' interest in learning Japanese has increased. Generally, Japanese language students who feel that they are not sufficient to improve their Japanese language skills continue their studies at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan. In addition to improving their Japanese language skills, Indonesian students in Japan also want to improve their Japanese language skills by preparing themselves to take the Japanese Language Proficiency Test (JLPT). The research methods used to conduct this research are the library and survey methods. The library method is carried out to obtain data and information relevant to research obtained from journals and articles on the internet. Meanwhile, a survey was conducted to obtain data on learning Japanese at Nihongo Gakkou. The study showed that learning Japanese in the Nihongo Gakkou in Japan influenced Indonesian students' JLPT results. This effect can be seen from the increase in the JLPT level, starting from a rise of 1 story, 2 classes, or even five levels when compared to before joining the learning program.

Keywords: The Effect of Learning Japanese Language, Japanese School, JLPT, Indonesian Student.

1. INTRODUCTION

Language is one of the elements that cannot be separated from human communication. Since birth, humans have been taught to speak according to their surroundings. Through language, humans can carry out daily activities more efficiently. Therefore, every country has a language as a characteristic of communication between people in the country itself. Indonesia in Indonesian, the United States in English, and Japan in Japanese. The character of a country makes the language in that country have its characteristics. We can find elements of speech in sounds, words, sentences, letters, etc.

One country that does not use the alphabet is Japan. So, in writing, three types of letters are used, namely hiragana, katakana, and kanji. Kanji characters are the result of adaptation from China, namely *hanzi*. While katakana is used for foreign pronunciation, in Japanese, the word "Starbucks" is written with katakana to become (suta bakkusu). According to Sa'adah (2015:31), for hiragana, at the end of the Nara period, the form of letters that were generally used in man'yooshuu, man'yoogana, changed to soogan. In the middle of the Heian period (794 AD - 1192 AD), the form of soogana was improved, simplified, and embellished to become hiragana. Japanese is a foreign language widely studied by Indonesian people, especially young people. According to Nurridha on the Kumparan, at least 128 million people can speak Japanese, which immigrants in Korea, Taiwan, China, the Philippines, and Brazil often say.

In Republika (2016), Indonesian students studying Japanese reached 870 thousand students. This figure makes Indonesia the second country globally that learns Japanese the most after China. Close diplomatic relations that have existed for 61 years and the number of Japanese companies in Indonesia affect Indonesians' interest in learning Japanese. More than 1,800 Japanese companies were established, and more than 19,000 Japanese citizens settled in Indonesia in 2017.

Based on this, Indonesian students' interest in learning Japanese is increasing, either self-taught through books or learning through teaching materials available on the internet or smartphone applications, taking the nearest Japanese tutoring program, or continuing to a higher level at D3/S1 majoring in Japanese or Japanese Literature.

Therefore, to meet the needs of Indonesian students' interest in Japanese language education, universities provide such study programs, for example, the University of Indonesia in Depok, Darma Persada University in Jakarta, and others. Generally, Japanese language learners who feel that they are not sufficient to improve their Japanese language skills continue their studies at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan. In addition to improving their Japanese language skills, Indonesian students in Japan also want to improve their Japanese language skills by preparing themselves to take the JLPT.

One of the efforts to assess how high the Japanese language skills of Japanese language students are is the most significant Japanese language test in the world, called the Japanese Language Proficiency Test (JLPT), which is twice a year. Apart from JLPT, there are other tests, such as Nihongo NAT-TEST and J-Test. NAT-TEST is a Japanese language test held by the organizing committee of the publisher SENMON KYOUIKU 6 times in 1 year in February, April, June, August, October, and December. The NAT-TEST exam consists of 5 levels: LEVEL 5, which is the lowest level, and LEVEL 1, which is the highest. The components of the exam questions consist of knowledge of the language (letters, vocabulary, grammar), reading, and hearing.

J-Test has been a practical Japanese language proficiency test since 1991. This exam is held six times each year. In the final assessment of the J-Test exam, there is no pass/fail system, but which level group the participant belongs to, Indonesian students who want to study directly in Japan can take a variety of short and long-term Japanese language school programs, namely as follows:

- 1) Japanese language school/*Nihongo Gakkou* is a school that provides Japanese language learning programs for foreigners. Some schools provide preparatory classes for high school/university
- 2) Vocational high schools/*senmon Gakkou*, intended for high school or college graduates who want to learn special skills such as graphic design, computers, cooking, management, and others. This school can also be followed for those who are already working and want to be entrepreneurs in accordance with the special expertise they want to have. Before entering *senmon Gakkou*, students who do not speak Japanese yet must attend a Japanese language school program (*nihongo Gakkou*) first.

- 3) *Daigaku diploma/tank*, intended for students who want to continue their studies to diploma school level for 2 years. Unlike Indonesia, *daigaku tank* cannot immediately continue their extension studies to university and must repeat from the initial level if they intend to continue their studies to university level.
- 4) *University/Daigaku*, is intended for students who want to continue their studies to the university level. Study programs at universities in Japan are the same as in Indonesia for 8 semesters. can take preparatory classes at *Nihongo Gakkou* to study Japanese and study university entrance exam materials. (source: <https://jin.co.id/tipe-school-di-japan>)

The number of students studying in Japan continues to increase. According to data released by the Japan Student Services Organization (JASSO), in 2019, there were 312,214 international students from all over the world studying in Japan, both studying in higher education (228,403 students) and studying Japanese at Japanese language education institutions (as many as 228,403 students). 83,811 students). The total number of international students has continued to increase for six consecutive years, from 2014 as many as 184,155 students to 312,214 students in 2019, with an average increase of 25,612 students each year. International students studying in Japan in 2019 were dominated by students from the Asian continent, especially China and Vietnam. Indonesian students in Japan in 2019 were 6,756 students or about 2.2% of the total international students in Japan. Indonesia occupies the 7th position of the countries that send the most students to Japan after China in the first position with 124,436 students, followed by Vietnam with 73,389 students, then Nepal, in 4th position Korea with 18,338 students, followed by Taiwan with 9,584 students, and Sri Lanka 7,240 students who are one position above Indonesia. Compared to the previous year (2018), Indonesian students studying in Japan experienced an increase of 479 students from 6,277 to 6,756. Among the 6,756 students, 5,204 are members of higher education institutions (a rise of 485 students compared to the previous year), 369 of them are students studying at the short-term education level (an increase of 5 students compared to last year).

The author observes the high number of students in Indonesia interested in learning Japanese at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan. The author is interested in knowing more about the views of Japanese language students from Indonesia who have studied in Japan on the impact of looking at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan to obtain a JLPT certificate. Therefore, the author decided to conduct a study entitled "The Effect of Japanese Language Learning at *Nihongo Gakkou* on the JLPT Outcomes of Indonesian Students in Japan ". The target respondents of this research were Japanese language students from Indonesia who had studied Japanese at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan.

2. METHODS

The research method is the way taken to complete the steps in the research. Sugiyono (2019:2) argues that "research methods can be interpreted as a scientific way to obtain valid data to be found, developed, and proven, a specific knowledge so that it can be used to understand, solve, and anticipate problems.

The data in this study consists of primary data and secondary data. Primary data is the result of JLPT, and secondary data is from Indonesian students studying at Nihongo Gakkou. Preliminary data were obtained to determine the results of the JLPT obtained by students studying at Nihongo Gakkou. In contrast, secondary data was obtained to determine changes in behavior learning at Nihongo Gakkou.

Based on these data, the method used in this study is a survey and verification research method with a qualitative approach. The survey method is used to find the effect of specific treatments. The survey method obtains data from certain natural (not artificial) places. Still, researchers carry out treatments in data collection, for example, by distributing questionnaires, tests, interviews, structured, and so on (the therapy is unlike in the experiment).

The treatment was aimed at secondary data, namely Indonesian students in Nihongo Gakkou and respondents in the study, by giving a questionnaire to obtain primary data, namely the results of the JLPT.

In this case, respondents who become secondary data carry out activities to answer questions from the questionnaire distributed to them. The questionnaire consists of 10 questions with multiple-choice answers. Furthermore, the survey results are calculated to obtain primary data.

From the answers to the questionnaire, information on the results of the JLPT was obtained for Indonesian students studying at Nihongo Gakkou during a specific period. Then, after the primary data was obtained, treatment was carried out to determine how much influence Nihongo Gakkou had in improving JLPT results.

Treatment is in the form of primary grouping data in JLPT results and grouping secondary, namely the length of the Indonesian study at Nihongo Gakkou. After being grouped, they are selected and sorted based on the lowest JLPT level, the most extended learning period, the highest level, and the fastest learning period.

Furthermore, these primary and secondary data were linked to obtaining the highest level of JLPT with the shortest study period in Nihongo Gakkou. Based on this treatment, the results of Nihongo Gakkou for increasing the level of JLPT.

The following method is the verification method, namely, collecting data generated through the evidence for the results of descriptive research with statistical calculations. The results of the evidence show that the data is valid/accepted. According to Sugiyono (2017:29), the method verification method according to Sugiyono (2012:8) is defined "as research conducted on a particular population or sample to test the established hypothesis."

Because this research is qualitative, there is no hypothesis, but the relationship is primary and secondary based on calculating the questionnaire results. Analysis of the questionnaire results is calculated according to statistics, then verified, and the results of the relationship between learning in Nihongo Gakkou with the results of the JLPT.

Verification is carried out in several stages, namely population determination, sampling, formulation of JLPT results, and categorization, followed by the length of the study period.

The population determination stage is all Indonesian students currently studying at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan or have finished studying in Japan and Indonesia. The following sampling step is from every student and alum of Nihongo Gakkou in Japan. Based on the level obtained, this sample is taken in numbers representing the population. Of the 1000 population determined from students and alums from Nihongo Gakkou, then take 150 pieces according to a category, both for Indonesian students who are still studying at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan and alums who have graduated, both those who are still in Japan and already in Indonesia. Then, each sample is verified along with its JLPT results. Verification is carried out to formulate the JLPT results, which are acquired to consist of levels N5 to N1.

The next stage is categorizing the length of the study period. The study period can determine the results of the JLPT level. The study period was divided from the shortest for three months to the longest for 1.5 years. Furthermore, all stages of verification and determination of primary and secondary data were used to obtain a link between the results of the JLPT and students studying at Nihongo Gakkou. Furthermore, it can be seen how significant Nihongo Gakkou in Japan is in improving the Japanese language skills of Indonesian students, and the JLPT results follow the JLPT level obtained.

The data collection in this study was carried out by distributing surveys via Google form to Indonesian students who had studied and completed the study program at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan. Some respondents live in Japan, and some have returned to Indonesia. This survey was conducted from June 13, 2020, to June 19, 2020, with 64 respondents who answered several questions from this survey.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Benchmarks on whether or not the learning program at Nihongo Gakkou affects Indonesian students is to compare the results of the JLPT level that have been achieved both before joining the program and after completing the study program at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan. Indonesian students contribute to participating in Japanese language learning activities at Nihongo Gakkou.

Based on the results of a survey of Indonesian students who are still studying, have studied, and have completed the study program at Nihongo Gakkou, can be described as follows:

3.1 Indonesian Students at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan

Indonesian students at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan are students from Indonesia who attend a study program at the Japanese in Japan (Nihongo Gakkou in Japan). The student must have graduated at least SMA/K and been equipped with Japanese in Indonesia for at least 150 hours or three months.

This amount is equivalent to the study period at the N5 level of Japanese. Japanese Language Level N5 is the Japanese Proficiency Test (JLPT), the lowest standard of Japanese language proficiency. As for the Japanese language, the JLPT has 5 levels marked with an N, meaning Nouryoku. The levels are N5, N4, N3, N2 and N1.

Indonesian students who go to Japan for Japanese Language Schools generally have basic Japanese language skills that can be used in Japan to communicate, especially when working part-time. While working part-time, Indonesian students study to get the target N2. Generally, the N2 level can be achieved after participating in the Nihongo Gakkou for 1 year, but some can reach it faster or longer in its implementation.

So that the influence of Nihongo Gakkou on increasing the results of the JLPT level of Indonesian students in Japan or who have attended it is very influential, it can be seen from the data that most of the respondents who were Indonesian students in Nihongo Gaku experienced an increase in the JLPT level, which was better than before joining the program. Based on the survey results, most respondents also felt that participating in the learning program made it easier for them to work on the JLPT questions.

Based on the data above, respondents who took part in the study program at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan with a duration of less than 3 months totaling 4 people, 2 of whom experienced an increase in the JLPT level achieved between before and after they joined the program, 1 person increased by 1 level, and 1 other 2 groups. Meanwhile, 1 respondent who studied for 3 months increased by 1 level from N5 to N4.

Meanwhile, 4 respondents who studied for 6 months, 1 respondent increased by 3 levels, 2 increased by 1 level, and 1 other did not experience an increase. A total of 30 respondents studied for 1 year, 9 of them experienced an increase of 1 level, 6 respondents increased by 2 levels, 6 others by 3 levels, and 5 people by 4 levels. 4 people did not experience an increase.

Meanwhile, from a total of 21 respondents who underwent the program for 2 years, 2 of them increased by 1 level, 7 people by 2 levels, 7 by 3 levels, 1 person increased by 4 levels, and 1 person increased by 5 levels. 3 people did not increase at all. As for 4 people who studied for more than 2 years, 1 of them increased by 2 levels, 1 other person increased by 4 levels, and 2 people did not experience an increase in the level of JLPT.

Based on the analysis above, out of a total of 64 respondents, there are only 12 respondents who did not experience an increase in the level of JLPT after they finished the study program at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan because of the difference in program duration and the ability of each person to absorb lessons differently.

There are also students who never took the JLPT test even though they studied at Nihongo Gakkou. This means that as many as 52 respondents, or about 81.3%, experienced an increase in the results of the JLPT level achieved after studying at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan. As for the 52 respondents, 16 of them (30.8%) increased the JLPT level by 1 level, 14 people (26.9%)

increased by 2 levels, 14 people increased by 3 levels (26.9%), 7 people increased by 4 levels (13.4%), and 1 person increased by 5 levels (1.9%). Therefore, studying at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan influences the JLPT results of Indonesian students in Japan.

In addition to studying at Nihongo Gakkou which was the initial factor, other supporting factors made Indonesian students who had studied at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan increase their JLPT levels. One of them is an internal factor, namely oneself. The different levels of willingness, effort, and ability of students to accept the material being taught make a difference between students in getting a JLPT certificate even though they are both studying at Nihongo Gakkou. The other supporting factors are external factors, namely environmental factors. Being in the scope of a school where students are both studying Japanese allows Indonesian students to discuss if something is not understood. In addition, living in Japan requires students to understand Japanese in order to survive such as buying food, taking public transportation, and so on.

The following is the average increase in the JLPT level of Indonesian students who have studied at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan if grouped based on the duration of the study program.

Table 1: Average Increase in JLPT Outcomes

Program Duration	Number of Respondents	Percentage Experienced Increase	Average Level
>3 months	4	50%	0.75
3 months	1	100%	1
6 months	4	75%	1.67
1 year	30	86.7%	2, 3
2 years	21	85.7%	2.19
>2 years	4	51%	1.5

Apart from studying in the program on why Indonesian students are interested in participating in the study program at Nihongo Gakkou, it is also necessary to know the reasons for each respondent consist of studying, working, getting scholarships, meeting Japanese idols, and so on.

Based on the data, respondents who chose the answer choices in the study category, namely "want to improve their Japanese language skills by studying directly in Japan," "want to continue their studies in Japan," and "get a scholarship," were 44 people (or around 68.7%).

Meanwhile, the number of respondents who chose the answer choices for the job category, namely "want to work in Japan or a Japanese company in Indonesia" and "get orders from the office to study at Nihongo Gakkou," were 17 people (or around 26.5%).

As for the environmental answer categories, namely "want to live in Japan" and "I want to live in Japan forever," there are as many as two people (or around 3.1%), and respondents who chose other categories with their answers as many as 1 person (or about 1.5%).

Therefore, it can be concluded that the reason why Indonesian students are interested in joining the study program at Nihongo Gakkou is because of the study factor.

The following are the results of a survey of Indonesian students participating in the *Nihongo Gakkou*:

1) Before joining the Japanese language study program at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan, to what level is your JLPT? Results:

From the questionnaire that the author distributed to 64 respondents via *google form*, the results obtained for the answers to the questions above are as follows:

- a. Respondents who answered "N1" were 2 people (3.1%)
- b. Respondents who answered "N2" were 3 people (4.7%)
- c. Respondents who answered "N3" were 13 people (20.3%)
- d. Respondents who answered "N4" were 9 people (14.1%)
- e. Respondents who answered "N5" were 11 people (17.2 %)
- f. Respondents who answered "Do not have a JLPT certificate" as many as 26 people (40.6%)

Based on percentage it can be seen that the answer that most respondents answered was "do not have a JLPT certificate". This means that Indonesian students who want to take part in a study program at *Nihongo Gakkou* generally did not have a previous JLPT certificate. This shows that Indonesian students want to get a JLPT certificate by studying at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan.

1) How long have you studied at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan? Result:

From the questionnaire, yes ng the author distributed it to 64 respondents via *google form*, the results obtained for the answers to the questions above are as follows:

- a. Respondents who answered "less than 3 months" were 4 people (6.3%)
- b. Respondents who answered "3 months" were 1 people (1.6%)
- c. Respondents who answered "6 months" were 4 people (6.3%)
- d. Respondents who answered "1 year" were 30 people (46.9%)
- e. Respondents who answered "2 years" were 21 people (32.8%)
- f. Respondents who answered "more than 2 years" as many as 4 people (6.3%)

Based on percentage, it can be seen that the answer that most respondents answered was "1 year" as many as 30 people (46.9%). This means that Indonesian students who study at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan generally study for 1 year.

This shows that Indonesian students participate in learning programs at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan with different durations, but generally study with a duration of 1 year.

2) Along with participating in the program, what categories of JLPT questions do you feel are easier to do?

From the questionnaire that the author distributed to 64 respondents via *google form*, the results obtained for the answers to the questions above are as follows:

- a. Respondents who answered "It is easier to do *bunpou* (grammar) questions" as many as 5 people (7.8%)
- b. Respondents who Answering "It do *moji/goi* (vocabulary)" as many as 10 people (15.6%)
- c. Respondents who answered "It's easier to do *dokkai* questions (reading)" as many as 5 people (7.8%)
- d. Respondents who answered "It's easier to work on *choukai* (hearing) questions" as many as 16 people (25%)
- e. Respondents who answered "All categories" as many as 25 people (39.1%)
- f. Respondents 3 people (4.7%) answered "Do not find it easier"

Based on percentage, it can be seen that the answer that most respondents answered was "All categories" as many as 25 people (39.1%). This means that along with learning In *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan, Indonesian students generally find it easier to work on JLPT questions in all categories, namely *bunpou*, *moji/goi*, *dokkai*, and *choukai*. This shows that studying at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan has an impact on students Indonesia in working on the JLPT questions.

3) After completing the study program, what level of JLPT did you get?

From the questionnaire that the author distributed to 64 respondents via *google form*, the results obtained for the answers the questions above are as follows:

- a. Respondents who answered "N1" were 6 people (9.4%)
- b. Respondents who answered "N2" were 25 people (39.1%)
- c. Respondents who answered "N3" were 22 people (34.4 %)
- d. Respondents who answered "N4" were 6 people (9.4%)
- e. Respondents who answered "N5" were 0 people (0%)
- f. Respondents who answered "Do not have JLPT certificate" were 5 people (7.8%)

Based on percentage it can be seen that the answer that most respondents answered was "N2" as many as 25 people (39.1%). This means that Indonesian students who have studied at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan generally have an N2 certificate after they finish the study program.

4) What is your current JLPT level? Results:

From the questionnaire that the author distributed to 64 respondents via *google form*, the results obtained for the answers to the questions above are as follows:

- a. Respondents who answered "N1" were 13 people (20.3%)
- b. Respondents who answered "N2" were 31 people (48.4%)
- c. Respondents who answered "N3" were 11 people (17.2%)
- d. Respondents who answered "N4" were 4 people (6.3%)
- e. Respondents who answered "N5" were 1 person (1.6 %)
- f. Respondents who answered "do not have a JLPT certificate" as many as 4 people (6.3%)

Based on percentage, it can be seen that the answer that most respondents answered was "N2" as many as 31 people (48.4%). This means that Indonesian students who have studied at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan generally have an N2 certificate at this time.

This shows that even though they have completed their study program at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan, Indonesian students are still trying to improve their JLPT level. It can be seen from the increasing number of respondents who answered "N1" and "N2".

5) In your opinion, does studying at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan have any effect on your JLPT results?

From the questionnaire that the author distributed to 64 respondents via *google form*, the results obtained for the answers to the questions above are as follows:

- a. Respondents who answered "Very influential" were 33 people (51.6%)
- b. Respondents who answered "Influential" were 26 people (40.6%)
- c. Respondents who answered "Less influential" as many as 1 person (1.6%)
- d. Respondents who answered "Very not influential" as many as 2 people (3.1%)
- e. Respondents who answered "Doubtful" as many as 0 people (0%)
- f. Respondents who answered "No comments" as many as 2 people (3.1%)

Based on percentage, it can be seen that the answer that most respondents answered was "Very influential" as many as 33 people (51.6%).

This means that Indonesian students who have studied at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan generally think that participating in the study program has an influence on their JLPT results. This can be seen from the number of respondents who answered "Very influential" and "Influential" a total of 59 people (92.2%).

- 6) If you feel that studying at *Nihongo Gakkou* has had an influence on your JLPT results, what do you think are the factors that influence this?

From the questionnaire that the author distributed to 64 respondents via *google form*, the results obtained for the answers to the questions above are as follows:

- a. Respondents who answered "Good school curriculum" as many as 4 people (6.3%)
 - b. Respondents who answered "Learning method or explanation teacher is easy to understand" as many as 10 people (15.6%)
 - c. Respondents who answered "Living in Japan made me trained to speak Japanese every day" as many as 43 people (67.2%)
 - d. Respondents who answered "The practice questions given are similar to the questions given came out on the JLPT exam" as many as 1 person (1.6%)
 - e. Respondents who answered "I answered no" were 3 people (4.7%)
 - f. Respondents who answered "Others" were 3 people (4.7%) with details of the answers as following:
 - 1) Respondent 21: "*Arubaito* in the service sector in various places has improved communication even more. There are many languages that have never been studied in books or universities in Indonesia. Besides that, they get along with native Japanese. Then have adoptive parents."
 - 2) Respondent 23: "Good learning methods, as well as direct explanations in Japanese, so that it demands that learners inevitably have to try to understand in order to follow the learning flow. Plus, living in Japan makes you trained to always try to read the kanji that you have learned or not."
 - 3) teacher's *native*
- 7) What are the reasons that made you interested in studying Japanese at *Nihongo Gakkou* in Japan?

From the questionnaire that the author distributed to 64 respondents via *google form*, the results obtained for the answers to the questions above are as follows:

- a. Respondents who answered "Want to continue their studies in Japan" as many as 20 people (31.3%)
- b. Respondents who answered "Want to improve ability to speak Japanese by studying directly in Japan" as many as 22 people (34.4%)
- c. Respondents who answered "Want to work in Japan or Japanese companies in Indonesia" as many as 16 people (25%)
- d. Respondents who answered "Get orders from the office to study in nihongo Gakkou" as many as 1 person (1.6%)

- e. Want to experience living in Japan" as many as 1 person (1.6%)
- f. "4 people (6.2%) with detailed answers as follows:
- g. Respondent 13: "Want to meet Watanabe Miyuki" (Japanese singer/former member of idol group NMB48)
- h. Respondent 26: "Gets a scholarship"
- i. Respondent 34: "Gets a scholarship"
- j. Respondent 53: "I want to live in Japan forever"

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion in the study, studying at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan, in general, influences the JLPT results of Indonesian students who have attended the program. Conclusion this is because factors support Indonesian students in improving their Japanese language skills, such as suitable learning methods, being taught directly by native speakers, and living in Japan, making Indonesian students try to improve their Japanese language skills. The increase in the level of JLPT also varies according to the duration of study and each student's ability. Some have increased by 1 level, 2 levels, or even 5 levels compared to before and after they joined the learning program. After completing the program, Indonesian students still need to increase their JLPT level. This is because everyone's ability to absorb lessons differs, and some students choose to skip the JLPT exam. Then, Indonesian students are interested in studying at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan, in general, to explore factors, such as wanting to improve their Japanese language skills by studying directly in Japan. Students feel that learning Japanese now at Nihongo Gakkou in Japan is more effective because they live in Japan, which makes them accustomed to speaking or seeing Japanese letters. The other reason is that they want to continue their studies in Japan, which is still in 1 category of "study factors." Before continuing their studies, they must practice their Japanese language skills at Nihongo Gakkou.

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